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COMPARATIVE STUDY OF A CONCEPTUAL DIRECT STEAM GENERATION SOLAR
POWER PLANT USING PARABOLIC TROUGH COLLECTORS AND OPTIMIZED
LINEAR FRESNEL REFLECTORS

THESIS

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DOCTOR OF PHILOSOPHY

by:

EDUARDO GONZÁLEZ-MORA

SUPERVISOR

PH.D. MA. DOLORES DURÁN GARCÍA

COMMITTEE

PH.D. MIRIAM SÁNCHEZ POZOS (UAEMex)
PH.D. IVÁN G. MARTÍNEZ CIENFUEGOS (UAEMex)
PH.D. RAM POUDEL (ASU)

CIUDAD UNIVERSITARIA
TOLUCA, MÉXICO, 2023

EXAMINER COMMITTEE:

President: Ph.D. Miriam Sánchez Pozos
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1st. Vocal: Ph.D. Ma. Dolores Durán García
2nd. Vocal: Ph.D. Iván G. Martínez Cienfuegos
3rd. Vocal: Ph.D. Ram Poudel

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Supervisor:

Ph.D. Ma. Dolores Durán García

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Articles

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- González-Mora, E., Poudel, R., & Durán-García, M.D. (2023). *A practical upper-bound efficiency model for solar power plants.* Journal of Non-Equilibrium Thermodynamics. 48(1). DOI: 10.1515/jnet-2022-0080
- González-Mora, E., & Durán-García, M.D. (2021). *Energy and exergy (2E) analysis of an optimized solar field of linear Fresnel reflectors for a conceptual direct steam generation power plant.* Energies. 14(4234). DOI: 10.3390/en14144234

Book chapters

- González-Mora, E., & Durán-García, M.D. (2023). *Aplicación de “La nueva ingeniería” en el modelado de un reflector Fresnel para la generación directa de vapor.* UAEM. Accepted.
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Conference proceedings

- González-Mora, E., & Durán-García, M. D. (2023). *Alternative methodology for modeling direct steam generation in parabolic collectors: A study case in Northeast Mexico.* In ECOS 2023, Gran Canaria, Spain. DOI: 10.52202/069564-0136

- González-Mora, E., & Durán-García, M. D. (2023). *Validation of an alternative methodology for direct steam generation modelling in parabolic collectors.* In EURO SUN 2022. University of Kassel, Kassel, Germany. DOI: 10.18086/eurosun.2022.12.06
- González-Mora, E., & Durán-García, M. D. (2022). *Propuesta de eliminación del coeficiente convectivo h para el modelado de flujo bifásico en concentradores parabólicos.* XVIII Congreso Ibérico y XIV Congreso Iberoamericano de Energía Solar (pp. 105-112). Universitat de les Illes Balears, Palma, España.
- González-Mora, E., Poudel, R., & Durán-García, M.D. (2022). *Maximum work rate extractable from the sun.* In International Conference on Thermodynamics 2.0 (pp. 57). Appalachian State University, North Carolina, USA.
- González-Mora, E., & Durán-García, M. D. (2020). *Comparativa del rendimiento teórico máximo y estimado de una planta solar de generación directa de vapor.* In CIES 2020 - XVII Congreso Ibérico e XIII Congreso Ibero-americano de Energia Solar (pp. 137-144). LNEG-Laboratório Nacional de Energia e Geologia, Lisboa, Portugal. DOI: 10.34637/cies2020.1.2014

Other research merits

During the course of the research leading to this present work, the author of this thesis has participated in several other publications related to solar energy, thermodynamics, and renewable energy topics. These publications are listed below. While not extensively discussed in this thesis, these publications significantly contributed to project development.

Articles

- Duran García, M. D., Jiménez García, J., González-Mora, E., Weber, B., & García-Vallejo, M. (2022). *Impact of Cost of Solid Biofuels on the Viability of their Application to Generate Process Heat in Mexico: A case of study*. Biofuels Bioproducts and Biorefining. X(X). DOI: 10.1002/bbb.2500
- González-Mora, E. (2021). *Evolution and further improvement opportunities of a non-imaging optics solar cooker design*. Academia Letters. DOI: 10.20935/AL3184
- Durán-García, M.D., Weber, B., Jiménez, J., & González-Mora, E.. (2021). *The application of solid biofuels as a source of process energy in Mexico: case studies using agave and coffee waste*. Biofuels Bioproducts and Biorefining. 15(2). DOI: 10.1002/bbb.2230

Book chapters

- González-Mora, E., Poudel, R., & Durán-García, M.D. (2023). *Solar radiation exergy model to study photosynthesis*. In Albert Reimer (Ed.), *Horizons in World Physics* (pp. 231-255). Nova Science Publishers.
- Rincón-Mejía, E.A., Islas, M. & González-Mora, E. (2023). *Potencial y límites de la energía solar*. In *Transición energética justa y sustentable*. CONACyT. Accepted.

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- González-Mora, E., & Rincón-Mejía, E.A. (2023). *A simple truncation criterion in CPCs using constructal theory*. In ECOS 2023. DOI: 10.52202/069564-0152

- González-Mora, E., & Rincón-Mejía, E. A. (2022). *Aplicaciones potenciales de un novedoso concentrador de óptica anidólica.* XVIII Congreso Ibérico y XIV Congreso Iberoamericano de Energía Solar (pp. 133-139). Universitat de les Illes Balears, Palma, España.
- González-Mora, E. (2022). *Optimal truncation criterion for compound parabolic collectors: A thermodynamic justification.* In International Conference on Thermodynamics 2.0 (pp. 57). Appalachian State University, North Carolina, USA.
- González-Mora, E., & Rincón-Mejía, E. A. (2021) *Optical Evaluation of the Tolokatsin-2020 High-Efficiency Solar Cooker.* In ISES Solar World Congress 2021. On-line. DOI: 10.18086/swc.2021.31.03
- González-Mora, E., Rincón-Mejía, E. A., & Morillón, D. G. (2020). *Diseño constructal de CPCs y la evolución de los diseños Tolokatsin.* In CIES 2020 - XVII Congreso Ibérico e XIII Congreso Ibero-americano de Energia Solar (pp. 131-136). LNEG-Laboratório Nacional de Energia e Geologia, Lisboa, Portugal. DOI: 10.34 637/cies2020.1.2013

These publications showcase the author's expertise in the field and highlight the diverse applications of solar energy, thermodynamics, and renewable energy technologies. The contribution of the different partners to the project development is acknowledged and appreciated.

Declaration of Authorship

I hereby declare that the contents of this thesis are my original work and have not been submitted in whole or in part for consideration for any other degree or grade at this or any other University, with the exception of explicit references to the work of others. This thesis was developed without any collaboration unless explicitly stated in the text.

Eduardo González-Mora
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Abstract

Concentrating solar power systems provide a promising option for generating energy from the Sun using thermodynamic cycles. The most commonly used solar power systems are parabolic trough collectors, which use thermal oils as the working fluid. However, the direct steam generation concept provides an alternative approach that generates superheated steam directly in the solar field without using thermal oil. Additionally, one can implement linear Fresnel reflectors instead of parabolic trough collectors. While some analyses of direct steam generation in both concentration geometries exist, there need to be more impartial comparisons of the operating conditions, specifically in Mexico. Therefore, we carried out an unbiased evaluation of several solar fields operating under identical conditions to determine the best option. The analysis considers two 10 MW power blocks employing a Rankine cycle with two and three steam extractions. Sixteen solar fields capable of delivering superheated steam at 400°C and 100 bar, with the mass flow restrictions in the absorbers taken into account, are analyzed. The comparison accounts for the effective concentration area, the nominal pressure at the inlet of each loop, the energy and exergy efficiency, and the hypothetical thermal storage size. Our findings suggest using parabolic trough collector solar fields with ten loops for superior overall performance in both power blocks. However, if pressure reduction is the primary concern, we can use three linear Fresnel reflector loops. For compact solar fields, we recommend using 2-loop of linear Fresnel reflector fields to minimize land use. Furthermore, we suggest using ten parabolic trough collectors loops to prioritize thermal energy storage and enable year-round solar plant operation, even though eight parabolic trough collectors loops would maximize thermal energy storage if that is the sole consideration. The analysis indicates that, under specific criteria, using Fresnel reflectors is advantageous compared to parabolic troughs, thereby providing an opportunity for further studies in this area and a foundation for studies of these technologies for Mexican operating conditions.

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